

The Macedonian mint at Susa (319/8-312/1 BC)

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This paper details a study of the coinage of Susa struck prior to Seleukos's annexation of the province of Susiana to Babylonia in 312/1 BC.¹ This coinage is divided into four groups defined on the basis of a progression of mint controls and the accompanying legend. The collective evidence suggests that the first three groups of this coinage were struck simultaneously in the period c. 319/8-318/7 BC to fund the campaign of Eumenes, preceding the confrontation with Antigonos at Paraitakene and Gabiene in 317/6 BC. This represents a downdating by up to seven years of the start of the Macedonian mint at Susa relative to that proposed by Price.² In contrast, the fourth group struck from a single obverse tetradrachm die, was an exceptional stand-alone issue, under the satrap Aspeias, 317/6-312/1 BC, possibly struck immediately preceding the annexation of the province of Susiana to Babylonia by Seleukos in 312/1 BC.

INTRODUCTION

The current understanding of the output of the Susa mint in the pre-Seleukid era relies on the thirty year old typology and analysis of Price.³ Yet the coinage throws up a number of uncertainties, not the least of which is the date of commencement of the coinage and the relative significance of the components of the coinage in the period prior to 312/1 BC,⁴ at which point Seleukos annexed the province of Susiana to his Babylonian domain.⁵ Presented below is a catalogue of the gold stater and silver tetradrachm coinage from the mint, including a die analysis aimed resolving some of the uncertainties attached to the current understanding of the coinage.⁶ The catalogue is sourced from the American Numismatic Society's PELLA online database,⁷ supplemented by coins identified in commerce.

CATALOGUE

The coinage is divided into four groups, identified by the number preceding each sequence type listing. Each group is defined by a progression of mint controls, and the associated legend. Within each group, specific types are identified by the digit following the decimal point in the type identifier. These types are distinguished by denomination (gold stater or silver tetradrachm), mint marks and the iconographic motif on the bowl of Athena's helmet in the case of the staters. The list of gold stater types precedes the tetradrachms in the catalogue, although as evident from the

¹ Referenced to the Macedonian lunar calendar year commencing September/October each year.

² Price (1991): 484-489 provided no explanation for his proposed chronology, other than to anchor the closing stage of the mint's Macedonian imperial output to the satrapy of Aspeias in 317/6-312/1 BC, via Price 3852.

³ Price (1991): 484-489.

⁴ Price (1991): 484 expressed reservation with his attribution and placement of Group 1 preceding Group 2 followed by Group 3. Le Rider (2007): 219-225 for an analysis of the uncertainties.

⁵ Refer Houghton and Lorber (2002): 67-77 for the subsequent coinage of Susa under Seleukos I.

⁶ The catalogue is not intended to be a corpus of all known examples. Rather, it represents a statistically significant sample for analysis.

⁷ <http://numismatics.org/pella/> at 16 November 2018.

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shared progression of mint controls, both denominations were struck contemporaneously (Table 1) in an interwoven manner. Gold stater obverse dies are prefixed Av to distinguish them from the tetradrachm dies prefixed with the letter A. In each denomination, reverse dies are numbered sequentially prefixed with the letter P. Coin weights are recorded in grams. All coins were struck from unadjusted dies. An asterisk adjacent to the catalogue number indicates a coin illustrated on the accompanying plates.

AV Staters

(Plate 1)

Group 1

c. 319/8-318/7 BC

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ to l., ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis.

1.1		Serpent on Athena's helmet	(Price 3825 corr.)
1.*	Av1	P1	8.57 London, BM 1872,0713.12; GC30.3825; Price (1991): pl. XIV, 3825; Larnaca Hoard IGCH 1472.
2.*	Av2	P1	8.53 CNG eAuction 40 (22 Oct. 2001), lot 64537. ⁸ Av2 - the bowl of Athena's helmet lack's a decorative motif, due to a flat strike, or possibly an engraving omission of this design element.
1.2		Duck on Athena's helmet	(Price 3826A)
3.*	Av3	P2	8.59 Roma Numismatics XIII (23 Mar. 2017), lot 187; Roma Numismatics 10 (27 Sep. 2015), lot 347; Roma Numismatics 8 (28 Sep. 2014), lot 463.
4.*	Av4	P3	8.52 New York, ANS 1965.77.100; Malko Topolovo Hoard IGCH 0853.
1.3		Sphinx on Athena's helmet	(Price 3826)
5.*	Av5	P4	8.57 Gorny & Mosch 203 (5 Mar. 2012), lot 134.
6.	Av5	P4	8.60 Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253848.
7.	Av5	P5	8.56 Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253847.
8.	Av5	P5	8.54 Heritage 3071 (6-7 Jan. 2019), lot 32006; CNG 61 (25 Sep. 2002), lot 478.
9.	Av5	P5	8.53 New York, ANS 1965.77.101; Malko Topolovo Hoard IGCH 0853.
10.*	Av6	P6	8.57 CNG 85 (15 Sep. 2010), lot 283.
1.5		Sphinx on Athena's helmet	(Price 3831)
11.	Av6	P7	8.57 CNG 58 (19 Sep. 2001), lot 175.
12.*	Av6	P7	8.52 New York, ANS 1944.100.35523.

⁸ Lot number as recorded on Wildwinds database: http://www.wildwinds.com/coins/greece/macedonia/kings/alexander_III/t.html at 16 Nov. 2018.

1.6				Sphinx on Athena's helmet	(Price 3828)
13.	Av6	P8	8.60	Heritage 3037 (4 Jan. 2015), lot 30903; Gorny & Mosch 219 (10 Mar. 2014), lot 123.	
14.*	Av6	P8	8.59	CNG 70 (21 Sep. 2005), lot 127.	
15.*	Av7	P9	8.53	London, BM 1987,0649.115; GC30.3828; Price (1991): pl. XIV, 3828.	
16.*	Av8	P10	8.64	NAC 84 (20 May 2015), lot 1453.	
1.8				Sphinx on Athena's helmet	(Price 3835 corr.)
17.	Av9	P11	8.56	Cambridge, SNG UK (Fitzwilliam) VI, 0510.	
18.*	Av9	P11	8.55	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253849.	
1.10				Sphinx on Athena's helmet	(Price 3839)
19.*	Av9	P12	8.57	New York, ANS 1944.100.35525.	
1.11	bee			Serpent on Athena's helmet	(Price 3838)
No examples identified.					
1.13				Sphinx on Athena's helmet	(Price 3841)
20.*	Av10	P13	8.52	New York, ANS 1944.100.35524.	

Group 2

c. 319/8-318/7 BC

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ to l., ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis.

2.1	ΛΑ -			Serpent on Athena's helmet	(Price -)
21.*	Av11	P14	8.56	CNG 85 (15 Sep. 2010), lot 298. Av11 die link to Group 3.1 (Cat. No. 48) - die here in intermediate state of wear.	
22.*	Av12	P15	8.25	CNG webshop 860681.	
2.3	ΛΑ			Gryphon on Athena's helmet	(Price 3844)
23.	Av13	P16	8.57	The New York Sale V (16 Jan. 2003), lot 99.	
24.*	Av13	P16	8.65	London, BM 1918,0103.1; GC30.3844; Price (1991): pl. XIV, 3844.	
2.4	ΛΑ			Sphinx on Athena's helmet	(Price -)
25.	Av14	P17	8.60	New York, ANS 1944.100.35522.	
26.	Av14	P18	8.61	Gorny & Mosch 203 (5. Mar. 2012), lot 137.	
27.	Av14	P19	8.47	Forum Ancient Coins SH10698.	
28.*	Av14	P19	8.55	Triton XX (9 Jan. 2017), lot 119.	
29.	Av14	P19	8.58	Heritage 3030 (5 Jan. 2014), lot 23725; CNG 93 (22 May 2013), lot 161.	
30.	Av14	P20	8.47	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18254310.	

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31.	Av14	P20	8.55	Oxford, Ashmolean HCR23754; SNG UK (Ashmolean) III, 3106.
2.5	AA			Serpent on Athena's helmet (Price 3845)
32.	Av15	P21	8.60	Vilmar Numismatics SKU12754; Leu Numismatik 1 (25 Oct. 2017), lot 58.
33.	Av15	P21	8.64	CNG webshop 750653.
34.*	Av15	P22	8.60	Pars Coins PCW-G6392; Roma Numismatics XV (5 Apr. 2018), lot 124.
35.	Av15	P23	8.59	Pars Coins PCW-G6391; Roma Numismatics XV (5 Apr. 2018), lot 123.
36.*	Av16	P24	8.54	Triton XV (3 Jan. 2012), lot 1129.
37.	Av16	P24	8.50	Triton XVIII (5 Jan. 2015), lot 470.
38.	Av16	P24	8.53	Heritage 3032 (10 Apr. 2014), lot 23127; Roma Numismatics 6 (29 Sep. 2013), lot 564.
39.*	Av17	P24	8.56	BM 1872,0713.48; Price (1991): pl. XIV, 3845; Larnaca Hoard IGCH 1472.
40.*	Av18	P25	8.53	New York, ANS 1967.152.313.
41.	Av18	P26	8.55	Berlin Münzkabinett 18254308.
42.	Av18	P27	8.62	NAC 96 (6 Oct. 2016), lot 1047; Gorny & Mosch 203 (5 Mar. 2012), lot 138.
43.	Av18	P27	8.58	Freeman & Sear Manhattan Sale III (3 Jan. 2012), lot 113.
44.	Av18	P28	8.61	Leu Numismatik 3 (27 Oct. 2018), lot 66.
45.*	Av19	P29	8.43	CNG eAuction 269 (30 Nov. 2011), lot 48.
46.	Av19	P29	8.48	CNG 87 (18 May 2011), lot 377.
47.	Av19	P29	7.38	CNG eAuction 377 (29 Jun. 2016), lot 24. Low weight due to removal of metal from obverse surface delamination on cheek, neck, and helmet.

Group 3

c. 319/8-318/7 BC

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ to l., ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis.

3.1	- No controls			Serpent on Athena's helmet (Price P-)
48.*	Av11	P30	8.51	CNG 90 (23 May 2012), lot 469. Av11 die link to Group 2.1 (Cat. No. 21) - die here in earliest state.
49.*	Av11	P30	8.57	Triton XV (3 Jan. 2012), lot 1130.
50.*	Av11	P30	8.52	Künker 111 (18 Mar. 2006), lot 6162.
3.2	AA	-		Serpent on Athena's helmet. (Price P207)
51.*	Av11	P31	8.49	Elsen 111 (10 Dec. 2011), lot 88.
52.	Av20	P31	8.50	Rauch 86 (12 May 2010), lot 326.
53.*	Av20	P32	8.60	London, BM 1872,0713.53; GC30.207; Larnaca Hoard IGCH 1472.
54.*	Av20	P32	8.57	New York, ANS 1944.100.35521.

Plate 1

THE MACEDONIAN MINT AT SUSA (319/8-312/1 BC)

Tetradrachms

(Plates 2-6)

Group 1

c. 319/8-318/7 BC

Obverse: Head of beardless Herakles r. wearing lion skin headdress.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ below, ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Zeus Aëtrophoros seated l.

1.4		(Price 3827)		
55.*	A1	P1	17.13	Roma Numismatics E-Live 1 (25 Jul. 2018), lot 118.
56.	A1	P2	17.13	Roma Numismatics E-Live 3 (25 Oct. 2018), lot 116.
57.	A1	P2	17.11	Roma Numismatics E-Live 2 (30 Aug. 2018), lot 180.
58.	A1	P2	17.10	Forum Ancient Coins SH31409.
59.	A1	P2	17.18	CNG eAuction 155 (3 Jan 2007), lot 25.
60.	A1	P2	16.96	Zurqieh SKU: mk664.
61.	A1	P2	16.94	Kırşehir Museum report 24 (Wildwinds online database http://www.wildwinds.com/ entry for Price 3827 at 6 Nov. 2018.)
62.*	A2	P3	17.10	New York, ANS 1944.100.35564.
63.	A2	P4	17.08	New York, ANS 1947.98.311.
64.	A2?	P4?	16.52	Miller (2010), pl. 6, 12; East Arachosia (Quetta) Hoard, 2002 (<i>CH</i> 10.275).
65.*	A3	P5	17.06	London, BM 1878,0301.140; GC30.3827; Price (1991): pl. CXII, 3827.
1.7		(Price 3832)		
66.*	A4	P6	17.08	CNG eAuction 383 (28 Sep. 2016), lot 53.
67.	A4	P7	17.10	Mike R. Vosper Coins MA-ID 757700844.
68.	A4	P8	16.90	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253850.
69.	A5	P9	17.11	Roma Numismatics E-Live 2 (30 Aug. 2018), lot 181.
70.*	A5	P10	17.17	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 47 (28 Jun. 2018), lot 232.
71.	A5	P10	17.12	NBJ The Art of Numismatics skug14.
72.*	A6	P11	16.75	Roma Numismatics E-Live 1 (25 Jul. 2018), lot 119.
73.*	A7	P12	17.12	Heritage 231918 (2 May 2019), lot 61005; Roma Numismatics XVI (26 Sep. 2018), lot 227.
74.	A7	P13	17.16	Pars Coins PCW-G6070.
75.*	A7	P14	17.09	NBJ The Art of Numismatics skug69; Daniel Frank Sedwick 12 (26 Oct. 2010), lot 1216.
76.	A7	P14	17.15	London, BM 2002,0101.938.
77.	A7	P15	17.08	Zurqieh SKU: mk671.
1.9		(Price 3836)		
78.*	A7	P16	17.21	Roma Numismatics XVI (26 Sep. 2018), lot 228.
79.	A7	P17	17.14	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 47 (28 Jun. 2018), lot 233.
80.	A7	P17	17.15	New York, ANS 1944.100.35565.
81.	A7	P18	16.84	Agora 69 (20 Sep. 2017), lot 12.
82.	A7	P19	15.81	New York, ANS 1944.100.35566.

1.12 (Price 3840)

No examples identified.

1.14 (Price -)

- | | | | | |
|------|----|-----|-------|--|
| 83.* | A8 | P20 | 17.15 | Numismatica Ars Classica NAC AG 88 (8 Oct. 2015), lot 575. |
| 84. | A8 | P20 | 17.07 | CNG eAuction 399 (14 Jun. 2017), lot 40. |

1.15 (Price 3829)

- | | | | | |
|------|-----|-----|-------|--|
| 85. | A9 | P21 | 16.91 | New York, ANS 1944.100.35569. |
| 86. | A9 | P22 | 17.00 | New York, ANS 1944.100.35568. |
| 87.* | A9 | P23 | 17.11 | Roma Numismatics E-Live 2 (30 Aug. 2018), lot 179. |
| 88. | A9 | P23 | 16.69 | CNG eAuction 397 (17 May 2017), lot 55. |
| 89. | A9 | P24 | 16.33 | VAuctions 265 (16 Jun. 2011), lot 13. |
| 90. | A9 | P24 | 17.10 | CNG eAuction 399 (14 Jun. 2017), lot 39 |
| 91. | A9 | P25 | 17.07 | London, BM 2002,0101.937. |
| 92. | A9 | P26 | 17.08 | Wildwinds online database http://www.wildwinds.com/ entry for Price 3829 at 6 Nov. 2018. |
| 93. | A10 | P27 | 15.73 | Roma Numismatics XVI (26 Sep. 2018), lot 226. |
| 94.* | A10 | P27 | 15.72 | CNG 72 (14 Jun. 2006), lot 439; Nelson (2010) pl. 3, 1630; 'Seleucus I' Hoard CH 10.265. |

Group 2

c. 319/8-318/7 BC

Obverse: Head of beardless Herakles r. wearing lion skin headdress.*Reverse:* ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ below, ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Zeus Aëtophoros seated l.

2.2 - ΛΑ (Price -)

- | | | | | |
|-------|-----|-----|-------|---|
| 95.* | A11 | P28 | 17.22 | Pars Coins PCW-G6495. |
| 96. | A11 | P29 | 17.10 | Elsen 125 (13 Jun. 2015), lot 37. |
| 97. | A11 | P30 | 17.10 | Münzen & Medaillen 44 (25 Nov. 2016), lot 136; Auktionshaus Christoph Gärtner 32 (24 Oct. 2015), lot 34143. |
| 98.* | A12 | P31 | 16.93 | CNG eAuction 165 (30 May 2007), lot 19. |
| 99.* | A13 | P32 | 14.56 | CNG eAuction 266 (19 Oct. 2011), lot 80. |
| 100.* | A14 | P33 | 17.17 | CNG eAuction 402 (26 Jul. 2017), lot 50. |

2.6 ΛΑ (Price 3846)

- | | | | | |
|-------|-----|-----|-------|--|
| 101.* | A14 | P34 | 17.08 | Roma Numismatics XVI (26 Sep. 2018), lot 229; Leu Numismatik 2 (11 May 2018), lot 86.
P34 - Zeus with crossed legs. |
| 102. | A14 | P35 | 17.15 | Baldwin's (6 Jun. 2009), lot 193. |
| 103. | A15 | P36 | 17.13 | Stack's Bowers Galleries 150 (8 Aug. 2009), Lot 8367. |
| 104.* | A15 | P36 | 17.10 | Paris, BnF 41838020. |
| 105. | A15 | P36 | 16.04 | Paris, BnF 41838021. |
| 106.* | A16 | P37 | 17.16 | New York, ANS 1944.100.35537. |
| 107.* | A17 | P38 | 17.14 | New York, ANS 1944.100.35559.
P38 - Zeus with crossed legs. |
| 108. | A17 | P39 | 17.07 | CNG eAuction 365 (16 Dec. 2015), lot 94.
P39 - Zeus with crossed legs. |

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2.7 - ΛΑ/Μ (Price -)

109.* A18 P40 17.00 Roma eSale 3 (30 Nov. 2013), lot 170.

2.8 ΛΑ Μ (Price 3847)

No examples identified.

2.9 Κ Α (Price 3850)

110. A19 P41 17.17 New York, ANS 1944.100.35562; Ankara Hoard IGCH 1399.
 111.* A19 P42 17.15 London, BM 2002,0101.940.
 112. A19 P43 16.88 Roma Numismatics E-Sale 40 (28 Oct 2017), lot. 115.
 113. A19 P44 17.12 Kenneth W. Dorney SKU: 4398; CNG eAuction 402 (26 Jul. 2017), lot 49.
 114. A19 P45 17.18 CNG eAuction 357 (12 Aug. 2015), lot 52; CNG eAuction 351 (25 May 2015), lot 109.

2.10 ΜΕ Α (Price 3851)

115.* A20 P46 17.03 London, BM 2002,0101.941.
 116. A20 P46 17.00 New York, ANS 1944.100.35563; Ankara Hoard IGCH 1399.
 117. A20 P46 16.60 CNG eAuction 363 (11 Nov. 2015), lot 53.

Group 3

c. 319/8-318/7 BC

Obverse: Head of beardless Herakles r. wearing lion skin headdress.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ below, ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ to r., Zeus Aëtrophoros seated l.

3.3 - ΛΑ (Price P208)

118. A21 P47 17.21 New York, ANS 1944.100.35538.
 119. A21 P48 16.95 Noble Numismatics 119 (23 Nov. 2018), lot 4603; Noble 118 (31 Aug. 2018), lot 1611; Noble 99 (17-19 Apr. 2012), lot 3336.
 120. A21 P49 17.23 Goldberg 104 (12 Jun. 2018), lot 3033.
 121. A21 P50 17.08 CNG eAuction 198 (5 Nov. 2008), lot 61.
 122. A21 P51 17.05 Christoph Gärtner 33 (10 Feb. 2016), lot 30063; Gärtner 32 (24 Oct. 2018), lot 34155.
 123.* A21 P52 17.07 London, BM HPB,p48.4; GC30.208a; SNG UK (Blackburn) VIII, 0510; Price P208a but incorrect coin illustrated by Price on pl. CXX - refer Cat. No. 128.
 124.* A22 P53 17.11 New York, ANS 1944.100.35541.
 125. A22 P54 16.78 New York, ANS 1944.100.35539.
 126. A22 P55 16.63 New York, ANS 1944.100.35540.
 127. A22 P56 16.80 New York, ANS 1944.100.35542.
 128. A23 P57 16.95 London, BM 1872,1202.1; GC30.208b; Price (1991): pl. CXX, P208a corr. This coin is listed as P208b in Price's text and in the BM catalogue.
 129.* A23 P58 17.05 New York, ANS 1944.100.35544.
 130. A23 P59 17.11 New York, ANS 1944.100.35543.
 131. A24 P60 17.06 Emporium Hamburg 72 (13 Nov. 2014), lot 147.
 132. A24 P60 17.05 CGB.fr Numismatics bgr_368571.

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133.	A24	P61	17.04	CNG eAuction 78 (26 Nov. 2003), lot 26.
134.	A24	P62	17.16	Rauch eAuction 9 (24 Mar. 2011), lot 63.
135.	A24	P63	17.24	New York, ANS 1944.100.35546.
136.	A24	P64	17.07	CNG eAuction 116 (15 Jun. 2005), lot 101.
137.*	A24	P65	16.67	New York, ANS 1944.100.35545; Abu Hommos Hoard <i>IGCH</i> 1667.
138.*	A25	P66	16.44	New York, ANS 1944.100.35549.
139.	A26	P67	16.98	Pegasi XXVI (15 May 2012), lot 96.
140.*	A26	P68	17.14	New York, ANS 1944.100.35548.
141.	A26	P69	16.72	CNG eAuction 409 (8 Nov. 2018), lot 119.
142.*	A27	P70	16.18	New York, ANS 1944.100.35550.
143.*	A28	P71	16.12	Noble Numismatics 89 (25-28 Nov. 2008), lot 3816.
144.	A28	P71	16.45	Paris, BnF 41838019.
145.*	A29	P72	17.09	Leu Numismatic Web Auction 2 (3 Dec. 2017), lot 150.
146.	A29	P73	17.17	CNG eAuction 155 (3 Jan. 2007), lot 28.
147.	A29	P74	17.20	Roma Numismatics E-Live 1 (25 Jul. 2018), lot 124.
148.	A29	P74	17.18	Gorny and Mosch 257 (15 Oct. 2018), lot 327.
149.	A29	P75	17.13	CGB.fr Monnaies 32 (6 Dec. 2007), lot 26.
150.	A29	P75	17.04	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18252071.
151.	A29	P76	16.98	Noble Numismatics 99 (2 Apr. 2009), lot 3255.
152.	A30	P77	17.16	Le Rider and Olçay (1988): pl. X, 176; <i>Akçakale Hoard CH</i> 8.201.
153.	A31	P78	17.00	Agora Sale 4 (20 Jul. 2017), lot 30
154.	A31	P79	17.20	Forum Ancient Coins SH09336.
155.*	A31	P80	17.05	Forum Ancient Coins GS82736.
156.	A31	P81	17.16	Oxford, Ashmolean Museum HCR24008; <i>SNG UK</i> (Ashmolean) III, 3237; Kuft Hoard <i>IGCH</i> 1667.
157.	A31	P81	17.09	Noble Numismatics 116 (21-24 Nov. 2017), lot 4259; Noble 107 (18-20 Nov, 2014), lot 3272; Noble 106 (29-31 Jul. 2014), lot 3351.
158.	A32	P82	17.02	CNG eAuction 188 (28 May 2008), lot 24.
159.*	A32	P83	17.20	CNG eAuction 299 (27 Mar. 2013), lot 151.
160.	A31	P84	16.45	CNG eAuction 356 (29 Jul. 2015), lot 31.
161.*	A33	P85	16.98	Stack's (10 Sep. 2008), lot 64.
162.*	A34	P86	16.69	Hirsch 256 (5 May 2008), lot 80; Hirsch 253 (27 Sep. 2007), lot 2120.
163.*	A35	P87	17.06	Paul-Francis Jacquier 44 (13 Sep. 2018), lot 83; Jacquier 43 (15 Sep. 2017), lot 86; Jacquier 41 (16 Sep. 2016), lot 58.
164.	A35	P88	17.10	Aegean Numismatics SKU: 071718.
165.*	A36	P89	17.14	Numismatik Naumann 72 (2 Dec. 2018), lot 53.
166.*	A37	P90	16.46	Triskeles 22 (15 Dec. 2017), lot 64.
167.	A38	P91	16.42	Pars Coins PCW-G4342.
168.*	A38	P92	16.85	Rauch 106 (10 Apr. 2018), lot 54.
169.*	A39	P93	15.72	Dr. Busso Peus Nachfolger 398 (28 Apr. 2009), lot 221.
170.	A39	P94	15.99	London, BM 1911,0704.122; GC30.208c; Price P208c.
171.	A40	P95	15.79	Le Rider and Olçay (1988): pl. X, 178; <i>Akçakale Hoard CH</i> 8.201.
172.*	A41	P96	17.18	Stack's Coin Galleries (18 Apr. 2007), lot 5052.
173.*	A42	P97	15.90	CNG eAuction 332 (6 Aug. 2014), lot 12.

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174.	A43	P98	16.51	Cambridge, <i>SNG UK</i> (Fitzwilliam) VI, 0528.
175.*	A44	P99	14.88	Heritage 231841 (11 Oct. 2018), lot 62003.
176.*	A45	P100	17.15	Noble Numismatics 87 (8-11 Apr. 2008), lot 4466; Noble 61 (4-6 Aug. 1999) lot 2607.
177.	A46	P101	17.14	Le Rider and Olçay (1988): pl. X, 177; <i>Akçakale Hoard CH 8.201</i> .
178.*	A47	P102	16.98	Kölner Münzkabinett Tyll Kroha Nachfolger 109 (16 Nov. 2018), lot 58.
3.4	dolphin	ΛA	(Price P212)	
179.*	A47	P103	17.01	London, BM 1967,1110.5; GC30.212; Price (1991): pl. CXX, P212.
3.5	cantharus	ΛA	(Price P214)	
180.*	A47	P104	16.82	Paris, BnF 41838022.
181.	A47	P104	16.94	London, BM 1907,0707.18; GC30.214b; Price 214b.
182.*	A47	P105	16.91	London, BM 1911,0409.214; GC30.214a; Price 214a.
183.	A47	P106	16.98	New York ANS 1944.100.35551.
184.	A47	P107	17.05	New York, ANS 1944.100.35552; Abu Hommos Hoard <i>IGCH 1667</i> .
185.	A47	P107	16.94	CGB.fr Numismatics bgr_325449; CGB.fr Monnaies 57 (20 Feb. 2013), lot 84; Burgan (25 Mar. 1993), lot 20.
3.6	star	ΛA	(Price P215)	
186.*	A47	P108	16.98	Stack's December 2009 Coin Galleries Sale (9 Dec. 2009), lot 38; Coin Galleries (August 2006), lot 159.
187.	A47	P108	16.63	London, BM 1985,1114.5; GC30.215; Price (1991): pl. CXX, P215.
3.7	club	ΛA	(Price P213)	
188.*	A47	P109	17.08	Zurqieh SKU: mk671.
189.	A47	P109	17.14	Le Rider and Olçay (1988): pl. X, 179; <i>Akçakale Hoard CH 8.201</i> .
190.*	A48	P110	17.21	New York, ANS 1944.100.35553.
3.8	-	Ξ	(Price P216)	
191.	A49	P111	17.24	Comptoir des Monnaies MA-ID 50835200158.
192.*	A49	P111	17.11	New York, ANS 1944.100.35528.
193.	A49	P111	17.09	New York, ANS 1944.100.35529.
194.*	A50	P112	16.95	New York, ANS 1944.100.35530; Olympia, Elis Hoard <i>IGCH 0176</i> .
195.	A50	P113	16.98	New York, ANS 1944.100.35531; Ankara Hoard <i>IGCH 1399</i> .
196.	A50	P114	16.93	New York, ANS 1944.100.35532; Abu Hommos Hoard <i>IGCH 1667</i> .
197.	A50	P115	16.87	Hirsch 338 (9 May 2018), lot 169; Hirsch 332 (20 Sep. 2017), lot 2152; Hirsch 326 (16 Feb. 2017), lot 1644.
198.	A50	P115	17.05	Stack's Coin Galleries (21 Feb. 2007), lot 49.
199.	A50	P116	17.04	Stack's Coin Galleries (18 July 2007), lot 432.
200.	A50	P117	17.20	Gemini X (13 Jan. 2013), lot 41.
201.	A51	P118	17.00	Akropolis Ancient Coins: Ancient Greek Coins No. 57. http://www.akropoliscoins.com at 16 Nov. 2018.
202.*	A51	P118	16.92	Triskeles 23 (6 Apr. 2018), lot 91.
203.*	A52	P119	17.12	London, BM 1876,0505.24; GC30.216; Price (1991): pl. CXX, P216; Kuff Hoard <i>IGCH 1667</i> .

3.9 Nike l./ P Ξ (Price P217)

204.*	A52	P120	17.03	New York, ANS 1944.100.35534.
205.	A52	P120	16.80	Numismatik Naumann 11 (29 Dec. 2013), lot 138.

3.10 P Ξ (Price P218)

206.*	A53	P121	17.13	CNG eAuction 414 (14 Feb. 2018), lot 97.
207.*	A54	P122	17.03	New York, ANS 1944.100.35533.
208.	A54	P123	16.68	Elsen 93 (15 Sep. 2007), lot 676.
209.	A54	P124	16.97	Oxford, Ashmolean HCR24009; SNG UK (Ashmolean) III, 3238; Kuft Hoard <i>IGCH</i> 1670.
210.	A55	P125	17.11	Comptoir des Monnaies MA-ID 50777600158.
211.*	A55	P125	17.07	CNG eAuction 198 (5 Nov. 2008), lot 62.

Group 4

c. 317/6-312/1 BC (most probably 312/1 BC)

Obverse: Head of beardless Herakles r. wearing lion skin headdress.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ below, ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Zeus Aëtrophoros seated l.

4.1 ΑΣΠΕΙΣΟΥ beneath extended right arm of Zeus. (Price 3852)

212.*	A56	P126	17.12	Stack's Bowers 149 (24 Apr. 2009), lot 2027. P126- Zeus with crossed legs.
213.*	A56	P127	17.16	New York, ANS 1944.100.72211; Bellinger (1963): 88, pl. III, 9; ex- Abu Hommos Hoard, <i>IGCH</i> 1667 buried 311-310 BC. P127- Zeus with crossed legs.
214.*	A56	P127	17.03	New York, ANS 2002.46.542; Hersh Coll.
215.*	A56	P128	16.93	London, BM 1921,0109.3; GC30.3852; Price 3852; Robinson, (1921): 37-38. ⁹ P128- Zeus with crossed legs.

⁹ This coin is that described as the type specimen for Price 3852. However, that illustrated by Price (1991): pl. CXII, 3852 is a publishing error for the correct ΑΣΠΕΙΣΟΥ reverse is paired to an obverse image from another coin. Refer BM 1921,0109.3; GC30.3852 for the correct obverse

THE MACEDONIAN MINT AT SUSA (319/8-312/1 BC)

Plate 2

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Plate 3

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Plate 5

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THE MACEDONIAN MINT AT SUSAN (319/8-312/1 BC)

Plate 6

Comparative Material
Babylon Group 2

- A - Price 3617, Akropolis Coins.
- B - Price 3619, ANS 1947.98.367.
- C - Price 3623, Münzkabinett Berlin 18251755.
- D - Price 3660, ANS 1935.117.1122.
- E - Price 3674, ANS 1944.100.80582.

Table 1. Susa groups 319/8-312/11 BC.

	Price	Mint Marks	Stater Av dies	Tetradrachm A dies
Group 1 ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ				
1.1	3825 corr. (S.)*		2	-
1.2	3826A corr. (D.)		2	-
1.3	3826 (Sph.)		1.33**	-
1.4	3827		-	3
1.5	3831 (Sph.)		0.33	-
1.6	3828 (Sph.)		2.33	-
1.7	3832		-	3.5
1.8	3835 corr. (Sph.)		0.5	-
1.9	3836		-	0.5
1.10	3839 (Sph.)		0.5	-
1.11	3838 (S.)		no example	-
1.12	3840		-	no example
1.13	3841 (Sph.)		1	-
1.14	-		-	1
1.15	3829		-	2
Group 2 ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ				
2.1	- (S.)	ΛΑ -	1.33	-
2.2	-	- ΛΑ	-	3.5
2.3	3844 (G.)	ΛΑ	1	-
2.4	- (Sph.)	ΛΑ	1	-
2.5	3845 corr. (S.)	ΛΑ	5	-
2.6	3846		-	3.5
2.7	-	- ΛΑ/	-	1
2.8	3847	ΛΑ	-	no example
2.9	3850		-	1
2.10	3851		-	1
Group 3 ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ				
3.1	P- (S.)	- -	0.33	-
3.2	P207 (S.)	ΛΑ -	1.33	-
3.3	P208	- ΛΑ	-	26.2
3.4	P212	dolphin ΛΑ	-	0.2
3.5	P214	cantharus ΛΑ	-	0.2
3.6	P215	star ΛΑ	-	0.2
3.7	P213	club ΛΑ	-	1.2
3.8	P216	- Ε	-	3.5

THE MACEDONIAN MINT AT SUS A (319/8-312/1 BC)

	Price	Mint Marks	Stater Av dies	Tetradrachm A dies
3.9	P217	Nike l., P Ξ	-	0.5
3.10	P218	P Ξ	-	3
Group 4	ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ			
4.1	3852	ΑΣΠΕΙΣΟΥ	-	1

* Motif on the bowl of Athena's helmet S.=Serpent, Sph.=Sphinx, D.=Duck or Dove, G.=Gryphon.

** Fractional numbers indicate dies shared between different types.

COMMENTARY

Table 2. Die links.

Linked Types	Die
1.3 1.5	Av6
1.5 1.6	Av6
1.8 1.10	Av9
2.1 3.1	Av11
3.1 3.2	Av11
1.7 1.9	A7
2.2 2.6	A14
3.3 3.4	A47
3.4 3.5	A47
3.5 3.6	A47
3.6 3.7	A47
3.8 3.9	A52

The sequence presented in the catalogue is summarized in Table 1.¹⁰ Six previously undocumented types are identified in the catalogue, three of staters (2.1, 2.4 and 3.1) and three of tetradrachms (1.14, 2.2 and 2.7). One new stater type (3.1) heading Group 3 lacks mint controls, but its attribution to the sequence and thus the mint is firmly defined by the obverse die link to types 2.1 and 3.2 involving die Av11 (Table 2). The other new types are control mark and/or legend variants of types previously identified by Price. Four corrections to Price's typology are noted. Gold stater type 1.1 (Price 3825) locates the mint controls beneath the left and right wings of Nike, rather than in the left field <LF> and beneath the left wing <LW> specified by Price. On stater type 1.2 (Price 3826A) the left most mint mark is located beneath the left wing rather than in the left field <LF> specified by Price. On stater type 1.8 (Price 3835) the mint mark beneath the right wing was misidentified by Price, as was the design motif on the helmet of Athena on the obverse. This correction is established by Münzkabinett Berlin 18253849 (Cat. No. 18)

which Price specified as a reference coin for the type.¹¹ It bears a sphinx, rather than a serpent, on Athena's helmet, readily identified on another example of this type from the same die (Cat. No. 17). Another correction occurs on type 2.5 (Price 3845) on which Price specified the location of the left mint mark to be in the left field <LF>, rather than beneath the left wing.¹²

Three of the sequence types are known from Price, but are not represented by any coins in the catalogue. The existence of stater type 1.11 (Price 3838) is uncertain. The coin attributed to this type by Price¹³ came from the 'L. Naville collection Geneva (dispersed)' its whereabouts unknown and no image of the coin was located. No other examples have been identified in commerce. Bearing the same mint controls, tetradrachm type 1.12 (Price 3840) is known only from Price's description of

¹⁰ Fractional die counts in Table 1 arise from dies used to strike more than one sequence type. For example, 0.33 represents a component of the coinage struck from a die that was used to strike three different sequence types. Among other things, the distribution of fractional die counts identified in Table 1 serves to emphasise the compact nature of the coinage, notwithstanding the multiplicity of sequence types.

¹¹ Price (1991): 485.

¹² Price (1991): 486.

¹³ Price (1991): 17 and 485.

a coin in the Batasani Hoard (*CH* 2.65), no examples being identified in recent commerce. Similarly, the existence of type 2.8 (Price 3837) relies on Price's catalogue entry of an example derived from the Phacous Hoard (*IGCH* 1678), although the whereabouts of this coin is unknown and no additional examples of the type were identified in commerce.

Die links occur between 19 of the 36 sequence types (Table 2). One die link is identified between groups, that of a stater die Av11 linking Group 2 in the name of Alexander to that of Group 3 in the name of Philip. This die link occurs on the opening issues of each and suggests that the two groups were struck contemporaneously, a point that is further substantiated by the $\Lambda\Lambda$ primary mint mark, which is shared by both groups. However, after the opening issues of Groups 2 and 3 each group has its own unique progression of secondary mint controls suggesting that both were struck in parallel, albeit on separate anvils, or in separate workshops, for the most part both presided over by a single official identified by the $\Lambda\Lambda$ mint mark (Table 1). Overall the pattern of die links identified in the catalogue indicates that the coinage was struck sequentially in each group, albeit as will be shown below, with a high probability that Groups 1-3 were struck simultaneously. Table 3 summarizes the die count in each group. In terms of die counts, gold and silver are approximately equally represented in each of Groups 1 and 2. In contrast, Group 3 is dominated by tetradrachms and Group 4 exclusively so.

Table 3. Number of obverse dies.

Group		Stater dies*	Tetradrachm dies
1	ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ	10	10
2	ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ	8.33	10
3	ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ	1.66	35
4	ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ ΑΣΠΕΙΣΟΥ	-	1
Total		20	56

* Fractional numbers result from a die shared between groups.

The number of obverse dies employed to strike each sequence type is summarized in Table 1. Only seven of the 36 types identified in the catalogue originate from more than two obverse dies. Stater type 2.5 and tetradrachm type 3.3 are the only types that were struck from 5 or more obverse dies. Half of the types in the catalogue were struck from a single obverse die. Of the latter, half were struck from an obverse die that was used to strike one or more other types (the fractional die counts in Table 1 and the die links of Table 2). From this analysis, we see that despite the plethora of types defined on the basis of iconographic motifs (staters), plus varying configurations and types of mint controls, only two types represent the most significant issues. Type 2.5 accounts for one quarter of the stater dies, while type 3.3 represents fifty percent of the tetradrachm dies. The dominance of two types, plus the die links observed with in each of Groups 1-3, point to each group being a compact emission, probably struck over a relatively short time. Group 4 was a small, short duration emission, originating from a single obverse tetradrachm die paired to three reverse dies.

Group 1

Two primary mint controls, , from types 1.2 -1.4, subsequently appears on the Group 2 coinage (types 2.3-2.7), the most prominent secondary control in Group 2. In the last third of the Group 1 a progression of new secondary mint controls appears, suggesting a change in the administrative structure and/or responsibilities in the mint. A similar phenomenon is observed in the last third of each of Groups 2 and 3 suggesting that the three groups were struck simultaneously from dies, which with one exception, were not shared between the facilities responsible for each group. Based on the distribution of types and observed die counts, the striking of gold staters and tetradrachms appear to have been equally spread throughout the Group 1 emission. However, with gold worth at least ten times silver on a weight for weight basis, this rough numerical equivalency in dies represents a significant value weighting to gold in Group 1.¹⁴

Group 2

The **ΛΑ** mint mark, accompanied by the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ, is the defining mint mark on all but the last two issues of Group 2. After the initial striking of coinage with only **ΛΑ** mint mark, a secondary mint control mint control disappears from the Group 1 suite of controls only to appear on Group 2 for most of the latter, argues strongly that the two groups overlap chronologically and were for the most part struck simultaneously on separate production lines, with separate official oversight, and no sharing of dies.

Group 3

The Group 3 coinage is defined by the presence of the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ accompanied for the most part by the same **ΛΑ** primary mint mark as that of Group 2. The opening issues of Groups 2 and 3 (Cat. Nos 21 and 48-51 respectively) share an obverse die, Av11, that is found in its earliest unworn state on 3.1, in an intermediate worn state on 2.1 and then in its most worn state on 3.2.

¹⁴ Le Rider (2007): 149 ... 'We do not know if the relative value of the two metals [gold and silver], which was theoretically 1 to 13.33 under the Persians, remained the same under Alexander or if it went to 1 to 10, as in Greece.' Also Bellinger (1963): 31 for a discussion of changes in this ratio through time.

This pattern of die wear on the coins struck from Av11 establishes that Group 3 does not post-date Group 2. Rather, the two are contemporaneous, a point reinforced by the shared $\Lambda\Lambda$ primary mint control. The argument for simultaneous striking of Groups 2 and 3 is strengthened further by the fact that both groups witness a change in mint controls in the last thirty percent of each emission, similar to the phenomenon observed in the last third of Group 1. The appearance of a symbol mint control in the last third of Group 1 (types 1.10-1.12) also finds a parallel in Group 3 (types 3.4-3.7 and 3.9) in which five symbol mint controls occur. This suggests the presence of a common approach to process control in the mintage of Groups 1 and 3 at this time, one requiring the presence of two Greek letter, or monogram mint marks, accompanied by a symbol mint control.

Group 3 is dominated tetradrachms following a small emission of staters employing two obverse dies, one of which was shared with Group 2. Type 3.3 accounts for eighty percent of the 29 obverse tetradrachm dies employed in Group 3, and forty-seven percent of all the tetradrachm obverse dies employed in Groups 1-4. This suggests a prioritisation in the striking of coinage denominations, with gold staters being the primary output in Groups 1 and 2 issued in the name of Alexander,¹⁵ while silver tetradrachms formed the primary output issued in the name of Philip III Arrhidaios. The observation of a single obverse die (A47) used to strike the last of type 3.3, plus types 3.4-3.7, indicates that the latter were struck in small quantity over a brief period.¹⁶ The final stage of the Group 3 emission is marked by the displacement of $\Lambda\Lambda$ primary mint control by the Ξ mint mark on a coinage struck from seven tetradrachm obverse dies; a relatively minor component of Group 3 compared to the preceding tetradrachm issuance from 28 obverse dies.

Figure 1. Philip III tetradrachms: number of obverse dies (observed).

¹⁵ Nominally this would be Alexander IV.

¹⁶ Indicative of the small volume struck in types 3.4-3.7, remarkably little progression of wear on die A47 occurred during its use to strike these types.

THE MACEDONIAN MINT AT SUSAN (319/8-312/1 BC)

The number of tetradrachm obverse dies observed in Group 3 places Susa as the third most prolific issuer of tetradrachms struck in the name of Philip III in the Macedonian empire (Figure 1),¹⁷ behind the mintage from each of the Imperial and Satrapal mints at Babylon and just ahead of that from Babylonia Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis). Based on the content of the Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664) the Macedonian Imperial mint at Babylon (Babylon I) struck all but perhaps the last issue¹⁸ of its Philip III coinage in the period 323-318 BC. In contrast, the satrapal mint at Babylon (Babylon II) commenced issuing coinage in the name of Philip III from 318 BC, during the satrapy of Seleukos. The latter's unofficial mint at Opis, Uncertain Mint 6A, commenced striking coinage in the name of Philip III from 318/7 BC bearing the archaized parallel legs depiction of Zeus, the same as that found on the Susa Group 3 emission. Seleukos struck this extensive coinage in the name of Philip III in both an official (Babylon II) and unofficial (Uncertain Mint 6A) capacity in order to strengthen his personal position and military support as the theatre of conflict between Eumenes and Antigonos moved from Asia Minor, through Babylonia, into Susiana in 318/7 BC.¹⁹ The similarity between the Susa Group 3 tetradrachm emission and that struck under Seleukos from his unofficial mint at Opis (Uncertain Mint 6A) suggests the possibility that the motivation for each coinage was similar, one that has its origins in the conflict between Eumenes and Antigonos.

Group 4

Group 4 consists entirely of tetradrachms struck from a single obverse die paired to at least three reverse dies bearing the legend ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ (Plate 6, 212-215). Although there are no die or mint controls links to the preceding groups, the presence of ΑΣΠΕΙΣΟΥ (of Aspeisas),²⁰ beneath the extended right arm of Zeus identifies this group as originating from Susa under the satrap Aspeisas. The latter was appointed satrap of Susiana by Antigonos following the executions in early 316 BC of Eumenes and his ally Antigenes, the preceding satrap of Susiana.²¹ Aspeisas remained in this role until 312/1 BC when Seleukos I annexed the province of Susiana to Babylonia.²² The Group 4 coinage from a single obverse die attests to a depleted treasury at Susa. This accords with the historical record that immediately on taking control of the treasury in early 316 BC, Antigonos moved its entirety, reputedly 15,000 talents, to his citadel at Kyinda in Kilikia.²³

Price associated the coinage bearing the name of Aspeisas with another group of silver coinage (Price 3853-80) characterized by a wreath symbol in the left field accompanied by a primary mint mark beneath the throne on the reverse.²⁴ However, a separate study has established

¹⁷ Figure 1 is a revision of that presented in Taylor (2015): fig. 3, and Taylor (2018): fig. 1 compiled from a die count of Susa Group 3 specimens in the collections of the British Museum and American Numismatic Society. Nine obverse dies were identified in the coins of these collections. The compilation of a more extensive catalogue, using coins in commerce increased the identified number of Group 3 tetradrachm dies at Susa by almost four-fold. The Ekbatana die count is updated from an unpublished study by the author.

¹⁸ The facing Helios symbol emission: Price P205-P206.

¹⁹ Taylor (2015).

²⁰ Bellinger (1963): 89 noted that the appearance of two names in genitive on the coin is without parallel on the Alexandrine series. It was probably understood as a coin 'of Alexander of (by) Aspeisas.'

²¹ Grainger (1990): 47-48 and Billows (1997): 106 & 376 citing *Diodoros* 19.55, 1.

²² *Diodoros* 19.100, 5.

²³ Grainger (1990): 48 citing *Diodoros* 19.48, 7-8 and 19.55, 1. Included in the 15,000 talents were 5,000 talents in 'coin and crowns.'

²⁴ Price (1991): 487.

unequivocally that this wreath group coinage (Susa Group 5) was the first of the Seleukid issues from the Susa mint, dated the period 312/11-309/8 BC.²⁵

Iconographic Style

The stater obverse dies can be categorized into three stylistic groups, the product of at least as many die engravers (Table 4). These three styles are shared across Groups 1-3 indicating a close temporal association, with the dies for each group sourced from a shared pool of engravers. With one exception (Av11), the obverse dies once employed in striking the coinage of a group were not transferred between groups. The presence of four different motifs of helmet decoration (serpent, duck, sphinx, and gryphon) on the staters of Group 2 is notable. Based on the sequence of associated mint controls, it appears that the choice of decorative motif was discretionary to the die engraver, rather than being a point of deliberate differentiation that formed a component of the mint's internal control process. In the case of Cat. No. 2 struck from die Av2, no decorative motif is visible, most probably due to a flat strike, although it is possible that the motif was omitted from the die. The reverse dies from which the staters were struck are of uniform style across the three groups, further reinforcing the inference that Groups 1-3 are closely associated.

Table 4. Stater dies: obverse style.

Style	Characteristics	Dies	Sequence Type
1	Flowing parallel wavy locks of hair. Serpent on helmet. Three small locks, increasing in size downwards, cover helmet rim above the ear.	Av1, Av15-Av19	1.1, 2.5
2	Locks of hair structured in three primary spirals of curls. Sphinx, duck, or gryphon on helmet. Two or three small locks of hair cross helmet rim above the ear.	Av2-Av10, Av13, Av14	1.2-1.13, 2.3, 2.4
3	Less structured wavy locks of falling hair. Serpent on helmet. Three prominent sigmoid locks obscure ear and adjacent helmet rim.	Av11, Av12, Av20	2.1, 3.1, 3.2

With one exception, the iconographic style of the tetradrachms, both obverse and reverse is notably uniform, although in the details of execution of the engraving a number of die engravers can be recognised.²⁶ The exception occurs with the depiction of the legs of Zeus, which for the most part is that of an archaized portrayal of parallel legs. However, on three reverse dies of type 2.6 (P34, P38 and P39) and the three reverse dies of Group 4 (P126-P128) the legs of Zeus are displayed with the right leg drawn back behind the left (that closest the viewer) in a crossed legs manner (Plate 3, 101 and 107 and Plate 6, 212-215). This variation in the portrayal of legs of Zeus is a precursor to the regular variation in the depiction found on the succeeding Seleukid era Alexanders from Susa.

²⁵ The Wreath Group (Susa Group 5) study is presented in an accompanying paper. Refer Taylor (2019): The Susa Wreath Group Alexanders: The First Step in the Transformation of an Anchor Seal into a Dynastic Emblem.

²⁶ Although subjective in its assessment, the work of at least ten engravers is represented in the tetradrachm obverse dies.

Although the parallel legs depiction preceded that of the crossed legs on the earliest Macedonian imperial issues from the mints of Alexander the Great, the adoption of the crossed legs depiction in the years after 325/4 BC was not universal. In some of the mints of the east, Susa, Babylonia Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis) and Ekbatana, the archaized depiction was retained until the closing years of the 4th century BC. At Susa it persisted on some of the Alexandrine style coinage of Seleukos and his successors into the 3rd century BC.

As noted by previous scholars the tetradrachms of Susa Groups 1-3 bear a strong stylistic affinity to some (but not all) of the examples of Babylon Group 2 dated to c. 325-323 BC.²⁷ A defining element of the obverse iconography of the Susa groups is the consistent depiction of two parallel wavy locks of hair extending from the lowermost lock of Herakles's hair onto the lion scalp, immediately above Herakles's ear. This iconographic detail occurs on all the Susa obverse dies, but is far less frequent on the Babylon Group 2 coinage, which shows a greater diversity of detail in the rendition of the same basic style. It defines the handiwork of a subset of the Babylon Group 2 die engravers, who in all likelihood were transferred from Babylon to Susa to establish a mint sometime after the striking of the Babylon Group 2. Plate 6, A-E illustrates five examples of a small component of the variously detailed styles represented in the Babylon Group 2 tetradrachm. This component was the foundation of that identified on Susa Group 1-3 tetradrachms, which was probably the result of the transfer of die engravers from Babylon to Susa after 320 BC. This explains the identical style of the Susa coinage with some²⁸ of that of Babylon Group 2, a point that confounded Price and led him to question the validity of his attribution of Babylon Group 2.²⁹

Group 4 (Plate 6, 212-215) represents a further development of this obverse style. However, in the reverse iconography, one detail in particular, sets this group apart from the preceding groups. It is the disappearance of the prominent footstool beneath the Zeus's feet, a distinctive element on Groups 1-3. This iconographic development is associated with the depiction of a ground, or exergual line upon which the feet of Zeus rest directly. This is the only occurrence of such a depiction in the Susa series. It sets the Aspeias issue apart, not only from the preceding coinage, but that which followed in the Seleukid era. Together with the unprecedented appearance of the name ΑΣΠΕΙΣΟΥ, unaccompanied by any mint mark, it establishes Group 4 as an exceptional, stand-alone issue in the mint's history.

STATISTICS

The sample of the coinage in the catalogue provides reasonable statistical coverage of the obverse dies (C_{est}), 0.83 for the staters and 0.86 for the tetradrachms (Table 5).³⁰ The distribution of obverse dies identified in the catalogue approximates that of a geometric distribution (Figure 2). This provides the basis for estimation of the original number of dies employed for the coinage ($Dest$),

²⁷ Price (1991): 454 and 484. Le Rider (2007): 219-225.

²⁸ It must be stressed that the emphasis here is on 'some' for it is apparent on detailed examination that Babylon Group 2 contains a far greater diversity of engraving style and detail than is exhibited in Susa Groups 1-3, a point that was apparently overlooked by Price in his analysis and summation.

²⁹ Price (1991): 453-457.

³⁰ This measure defines the how representative of the original coinage is the sample. It indicates that for the staters there is a 17% probability ($1-C_{est}$) of additional coins yielding a previously unidentified obverse die, while the equivalent probability for the tetradrachms is somewhat less at 14%.

albeit within a larger uncertainty (95% confidence interval)³¹ than would be the case for a larger sample of the coinage. Based on the geometric model of Esty,³² it is estimated that 32 stater obverse dies and 86 tetradrachm obverse dies were employed in the coinage. From these estimates of the original number of dies an approximate estimation of the volume of the coinage is possible.³³ The gold stater coinage is estimated to have amounted to 106 Attic talents of gold,³⁴ although within the uncertainty attached to the estimate of original dies this could be as low as 79 talents, or as high as 142 talents, based on the 95% confidence interval. A similar calculation for the tetradrachms yields an estimated coinage volume of 1,135 Attic talents of silver within an uncertainty range of 963-1,332 talents. Using a 10:1 gold to silver value ratio³⁵ the total coinage approximated 2,193 Attic talents of silver equivalent within a 95% confidence interval of 1,757-2,755 Attic talents silver equivalent. By these estimates, it is apparent that the coinage was of an appreciable volume and value, almost evenly split between gold and silver on a total value basis, albeit with the gold emissions dominating Groups 1 and 2, while silver was the prevailing metal of Groups 3 and 4.

Table 5. Catalogue statistics.

	Staters Av dies	Tetradrachms A dies
Sample size (<i>n</i>)	54	161
Observed Dies (<i>d</i>)	20	56
Singletons (<i>d</i> ₁)	9	23
Characteristic Index (<i>n/d</i>)	2.70	2.88
Coverage (<i>C_{est}</i>)	0.83	0.86
Estimated Dies (<i>D_{est}</i>)	31.8	85.9
95% Confidence Interval	23.8-42.5	73.0-101.0
Estimated Coinage (no. of coins)	c. 320,000	c. 1,720,000
Attic Talents of silver equivalent	1,058	1,135

³¹ Esty (2006): 360, formula 4. This confidence interval defines the range within which a new estimate of *D_{est}* based on a new sample of the coinage will fall 95% of the time.

³² Esty (2011).

³³ Callataj (2011) based on an average stater obverse die productivity of 10,000 coins and an average tetradrachm die productivity of 20,000 coins.

³⁴ All figures quoted in the text have been rounded to the nearest whole die and nearest whole talent.

³⁵ Le Rider (2007): 149.

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Figure 2. Distribution of obverse dies.

METROLOGY

The weight distribution of the gold staters is illustrated on Figure 3. After removing from consideration two worn and damaged underweight staters (Cat. Nos. 22 and 47), each more than three standard deviations below the mean weight, the weight distribution of the gold staters is tightly constrained with coincident mean, median and modal weights of 8.56-8.57 grams in a distribution with a small standard deviation of 0.05 grams (Table 6). The gold coinage was weight adjusted with precision to a weight standard of 8.6 grams per stater.

Table 6. Weight distribution after 3σ truncation.

	Number (n)	Mean (gm)	Median (gm)	Mode (gm)	σ (gm)
Av Staters	52	8.56	8.56	8.57	0.046
Tetradrachms	159	16.99	17.07	17.10	0.240

The weight distribution of tetradrachms is illustrated on Figure 4. After removing from consideration two worn underweight coins (Cat. Nos. 99 and 175), three standard deviations below the mean weight, the truncated distribution exhibits a mean weight of 16.99 grams, a median weight of 17.07 grams and a modal weight of 17.11 grams (Table 6). The resultant distribution has a moderate standard deviation of 0.24 grams and negative skew of -2.1. This distribution conforms to that expected from *al pezzo* weight adjustment to a weight standard of around 17.15 grams per tetradrachm. This slightly reduced Attic weight standard is consistent with the mintage of the coinage in the decade following the death of Alexander the Great, prior to which precise weight

adjustment to 17.20 grams was the norm.

Figure 3. Staters: weight distribution

Seven underweight tetradrachms in the range 15.72-15.99 grams warrant comment. These are almost three standard deviations removed from the mean weight. One of these coins (Cat. No. 94) prompted the suggestion that some of the Susa issues were struck ‘on the native Persic standard.’³⁶ The coins in question are in good undamaged condition, with no evidence of corrosion, or porosity and show only light to moderate wear. The underweight coins (Cat. Nos. 82, 93, 94, 169, 170, 171 and 173) constitute less than four percent of the total sample. The low weights may reflect random examples of poor weight adjustment, for the most part occurring late in the emissions of Groups 1-3. However, two examples originated from the same die pair (A10/P27), the last of the Group 1 sequence, while another two of type 3.3 were struck from the same obverse die (A39), so that the possibility that these examples represent either deliberately, or fraudulently underweight striking cannot be excluded. Either way, there is no evidence in the data (e.g. a bimodal weight distribution) to support the premise of a ‘native Persic standard’ in the coinage.

³⁶ Classical Numismatic Group Inc. <https://www.cngcoins.com/Coin.aspx?CoinID=84210> (at 16 Nov. 2018) ... ‘There is a wide variation in the weights of the early Alexandrine tetradrachms of Susa, with some in the normal Attic weight range and others falling in the mid-16 g to mid-15 g range. Unfortunately, the early coinage of Alexander III from Susa is fairly rare, pre-empting a good understanding of these series. A plausible theory is that the lower weight specimens were struck on the native Persic standard. We know that at other mints, such as Babylon, the native, Persic weight Baal-lion staters were produced alongside the Alexandrine coinage, ostensibly for local use. It is possible, therefore, that a local coinage was also made on this standard at Susa, but for some reason was struck in Alexandrine type.’

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Figure 4. Tetradrachms: weight distribution.

HOARDS

Documented hoard occurrences of the coinage are identified in Table 7.³⁷ A wide dispersal of the coinage is indicated by find locations that range from Romania, Bulgaria, and Greece in the northwest, through Asia Minor, Cyprus, Phoenicia, and Mesopotamia, into Egypt in the south and modern-day Iran and Pakistan to the east.

Table 7. Hoard occurrences: Susa Groups 1-4 coinage.

Hoard	IGCH or CH	Burial BC	In the name of Alexander	Philip
<i>Av Staters</i>				
Larnaca, 1870	1472	c. 300	2	1
Malko Topolovo, 1940	0853	285-275	2	-
<i>Tetradrachms</i>				
Myriophyton, 1932-1933	0432	325-300	1	-
Abu Hommos, 1919	1667	311-310	1	3
Egypt, 1894	1669	c. 310	1	2
Byblus 1931	1515	c. 309-308	-	2

³⁷ Online IGCH database <http://coinhoards.org/> at 8 November 2018.

Hoard	IGCH or CH	Burial BC	In the name of	
			Alexander	Philip
Kuft, 1875	1670	c. 310-305	2	1
Chorsabad, 1934?	1754	310-305	-	2
Aghios Ioannis, 1949	1470	c. 305	-	1
Kato Paphos, 1965	1471	c. 305	-	1
Messene, 1922	0095	305-300	-	1
Mosul, 1862-3?	1756	305-270	1	-
Karaman, 1969	1398	c. 300	1	-
Pasargadae, 1963	1793	c. 300	2	1
Ankara, c. 1913	1399	290-285	2	1
Prilepec 1950	0448	c. 280	-	1
Pasargadae, 1963	1794	c. 280	2	1
Thessalonica, before 1897	0444	c. 280	-	2
Pontoleibade-Kilkis, 1961	0445	c. 280	1	1
Mersin, 1963	1424	c. 280	-	2
Phacous, 1956	1678	c. 283	1	1
Kaswin, 1964	1796	c. 275	1	-
Kirazli, 1939	1369	c. 235	1	7
Olympia, Elis, 1922	0176	235-225	-	1
Anadol, 1895	0866	228-220	1	1
Batasani, 1971	CH 2.65	c. 280	2	1
Akçakale Hoard 1958	CH 8.201	317/6	-	4
Thessaly 1973	CH 10.55	300-275	-	1
Karadege Mevki, Turkey	CH 10.245	310-300	2	-
'Seleucus I' Hoard 2005	CH 10.265	c. 281	3	1
Unknown Findspot 2003	CH 10.274	c. 210	2	-
Quetta, Pakistan 2002	CH 10.275	206-200	1	-

The earliest documented find is that of four Group 3 tetradrachms (three of type 3.3 and one of type 3.7) in the Akçakale Hoard (CH 8.201) dated to 317/6 BC,³⁸ providing a *terminus ante quem* for the coinage of Groups 1-3. Coins in the catalogue from documented hoards are noted in Table 8, including the obverse die from which each was struck. Dies down to the last of the Group 4 are represented in the finds dated prior to the last decade of the 4th century BC, supporting the historical record of the satrapy of Aspeias who was responsible for the Group 4 emission.

Most notable from the hoard record is the complete absence of the coinage of Susa from the Demanhur Hoard (IGCH 1664) that closed in 318 BC. Every Macedonian imperial mint operating in the east prior to 320 BC, ranging from Cyprus, Phoenicia and Syria to Babylonia is represented in the Demanhur Hoard, including that of the most minor mints of Karne and Byblos (Berytos of Price).³⁹ The absence of Susa coinage from this monumental hoard is most significant, for it is

³⁸ Le Rider and Olçay (1988): 48 'On peut donc admettre, semble-t-il, que le trésor a été enfoui en 317, ou peut-être tout au début de 316.'

³⁹ Newell (1923) and Le Rider (2007): 147. On the reattribution of the Berytos coinage to Byblos refer Taylor (in prep): On the Reattribution of the Berytos Alexanders to Byblos.

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apparent that there was no impediment to the circulation of the coinage into Egypt down to the last decade of the 4th century BC; evidenced by the content of Abu Hommos (IGCH 1667) and Kuf t (IGCH 1670) Hoards (Tables 7 and 8). Based on the hoard record, it is most plausible that the Susa emission did not commence prior to 320 BC, while a start date as late as 318 BC would be consistent with the data. In the absence of the coinage from the Demanhur Hoard we find *terminus post quem* of c. 320-318 BC for the coinage.

Table 8. Hoard occurrences: catalogue coins.

Group	Cat. No.	Die	Hoard	BC
1.1	1	Av1	Larnaca IGCH 1472	c. 300
1.2	4	Av4	Malko Topolovo IGCH 0853	285-275
1.3	9	Av5	Malko Topolovo IGCH 0853	285-275
2.5	39	Av17	Larnaca IGCH 1472	c. 300
3.2	53	Av20	Larnaca IGCH 1472	c. 300
1.4	64	A2	Quetta, Pakistan CH 10.275.	c. 206
1.15	94	A10	'Seleucus I' Hoard CH 10.265	c. 281
2.9	110	A20	Ankara IGCH 1399	290-285
2.10	116	A20	Ankara IGCH 1399	290-285
3.3	137	A24	Abu Hommos IGCH 1667	311-310
3.3	152	A30	Akçakale CH 8.201	317-316
3.3	156	A31	Kuft IGCH 1670	310-305
3.3	171	A40	Akçakale CH 8.201	317/6
3.3	177	A46	Akçakale CH 8.201	317-316
3.5	184	A47	Abu Hommos Hoard IGCH 1667	311-310
3.7	189	A47	Akçakale CH 8.201	317-316
3.8	194	A50	Olympia, Elis IGCH 0176	235-225
3.8	195	A50	Ankara IGCH 1399	290-285
3.8	196	A50	Abu Hommos IGCH 1667	311-310
3.8	203	A52	Kuft IGCH 1670	310-305
3.10	209	A54	Kuft IGCH 1670	310-305
4.1	213	A56	Abu Hommos IGCH 1667	311-310

CHRONOLOGY

The relative chronology of Groups 1-3 is established from the die study and typological analysis (Table 9). Key indicators of the progression of simultaneous striking of these three groups include the linking obverse die Av11 at the start of Groups 2 and 3, the subsequent transfer of the secondary mint control from Group 1 to Group 2, the shared $\Lambda\Lambda$ primary mint control on both Groups 2 and 3, and finally the introduction of a new suite of mint controls in the last stages of each of Groups 1-3, including symbol mint controls in the closing stages of Groups 1 and 3. Furthermore, Groups 1-3 maintain shared conventions, die engravers (Table 4) and iconographic style throughout.

Table 9. Relative chronology.

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Indicator
1.1-1.4	2.1-2.2	3.1-3.2	Av11 die link 2.1, 3.1, 3.2
1.5-1.7	2.3-2.8	3.3	transfer Gp. 1 to Gp. 2 AA primary mint mark on 2.1-2.8 and 3.2-3.7
		3.4-3.7	Symbol controls 3.4-3.7
1.8-1.15	2.9-2.10	3.8-3.10	New mint marks appear on Gps. 1-3, incl. symbols on 1.10-1.12 and 3.9.

Without any explanation, Price dated Group 1 to the period *c.* 325-*c.* 320 BC. This date is problematic in light of the hoard evidence, more so in view of the contemporaneity of Groups 1-3 established from the die and typological analysis. Group 3, and by implication the chronologically associated Groups 1 and 2, are identified with the reign of Phillip III Arrhidaios from June 323 to December 317 BC. The absence of any of Groups 1-3 in the Demanhur Hoard (*IGCH* 1664) buried in 318 BC suggests that this coinage was struck in the last few years of the reign of Philip III, for the coinage appears in Egyptian hoards dating to the closing decade of the 4th century BC, at which time circulation from Susa into Egypt would have been more problematic than in the years preceding the burial of the Demanhur Hoard. Moreover, Group 3 coinage is represented in the Akçakale Hoard (*CH* 8.201), which dates to around 2 years after the Demanhur Hoard, demonstrating that the coinage rapidly found its way into northern Mesopotamia, 1200 km to the northwest of Susa. Weighing the evidence, it appears most probable that the mint at Susa commenced issuing the Group 1-3 coinage in the name of both Alexander and Philip after 319/8 BC with the coinage concluded upon, or shortly after the murder of Philip III Arrhidaios in December 317 BC.⁴⁰

This dating indicates that the establishment of a mint at Susa occurred after the Treaty of Triparadeisos in 320 BC. The latter resulted in a revised partitioning of responsibilities in the empire, accompanied by the reorganization of the administration of the Alexander mints in the east.⁴¹ It certainly involved the closure of some mints in Cyprus, Phoenicia, and Syria, accompanied by the opening of a satrapal mint at Babylon (Babylon II). The commissioning of a Macedonian

⁴⁰ Bellinger (1951): 45 reached similar conclusion, based on the hoard data. His reasoning appears to have been overlooked by Price (1991).

⁴¹ Taylor (2015):47.

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mint at Susa may have occurred under the supervision of the satrap Antigenes⁴² to whom Susiana was allocated at Triparadeisos. In addition to his satrapal responsibilities, Antigenes was the commander of the *Argyraspides* (Silver Shields), who fatefully sided with Eumenes in the Second War of the *Diadochi* (318-316 BC).⁴³

Group 4 provides a firm chronological marker for the last of Macedonian imperial issues from Susa. It bears the genitive form name ΑΣΠΕΙΣΟΥ (of Aspeisas), beneath the extended right arm of Zeus.⁴⁴ Aspeisas was appointed satrap of Susiana by Antigonos, the *strategos* of Asia, in 317/6 BC following the defeat and execution of Eumenes and his ally Antigenes, the former satrap of Susiana.⁴⁵ Aspeisas occupied this role for five years until the province of Susiana was annexed to Babylonia by Seleukos in 312/1 BC. Into this period Group 4 must be dated, a point confirmed by the appearance of Cat. No. 213 in the Abu Hommos (*IGCH* 1667) buried in 311-310 BC.

INTERPRETATION

In 317 BC the theatre of conflict between Eumenes and Antigonos moved into the region Susiana and the adjacent provinces of Peris and Media. This culminated in two great battles at Paraitakene in late 317 BC and Gabiene in early 316 BC.⁴⁶ By the summer of 317 BC the armies of Eumenes and his allies among the eastern satraps had assembled at Susa preparatory to the confrontation with Antigonos. Eumenes held the authorization from the kings (Phillip III Arrhidaios and Alexander IV) to draw on the royal treasury at Susa in support of the royalist cause.⁴⁷ The requirement for funding of the war effort led by Eumenes, with whom Antigenes the satrap of Susiana had allied himself, explains the substantial volume of the Groups 1-3 coinage. A large volume of gold staters issued in the name Alexander (IV), accompanied by the equal weighting of silver tetradrachms in the name of Philip (III), was an expression of his loyalty and that of the Greek veterans, in particular the *Argyraspides*, that formed the core of his army. Most plausibly, Groups 1-3 were struck preparatory to the assembly of the armies of Eumenes and his allies at Susa.⁴⁸

When Antigonos and his army reached Susa in 317 BC, access to the treasury was denied to him on the instruction of Eumenes,⁴⁹ forcing Antigonos to march his army to Ekbatana in order to

⁴² Billows (1990): 70..

⁴³ Billows (1990): 85 and 101-103 and Bosworth (2002): 109 and 114.

⁴⁴ Bellinger (1963): 89 noted that the appearance of two names in genitive on the coin is without parallel on the Alexandrine series. It was probably understood as a coin 'of Alexander of (by) Aspeisas.'

⁴⁵ *Diodoros* 19.55, 1. Billows (1997): 106 & 376.

⁴⁶ Bosworth (2002): 98-165 and 282 for a comprehensive account of events in Susiana and the eastern satrapies at this time. Also Billows (1990): 81-109, Bosworth (2002): 98-168 and Waterfield (2011): 94-102.

⁴⁷ *Diodoros* 19.15, 1-5, Billows (1990): 90, Bosworth (2002): 114, Romm (2011): 246 and Waterfield (2011): 96.

⁴⁸ *Diodoros* 19.1, 3 and 19.18, 1. Bosworth (2002): 114 and n. 66-67 'Eumenes, however, had the advantage that he was the only person authorized to draw money from the royal treasuries, and Xenophilus, the treasurer at Susa was scrupulous in implementing the royal instructions. That gave Eumenes the resources to pay his Macedonians for six months and he was able to give Eudamus the massive sum of 200 talents for the maintenance of his elephants.'

⁴⁹ *Diodoros* 19.17, 3, and 19.18, 1. Bosworth (2002): 116 and n.75. This denial of access to the royal treasury at Susa, and the events which preceded it, provide insight into the management and operation of the royal treasuries (and associated mints) at the time. It belies the belief that the Satraps were free to utilize royal treasuries and mint coinage as they saw fit. Antigonos held the elevated status of *Strategos* of Asia, yet he was denied access to the Susa treasury because he lacked the royal consent to do so. Ironically, his subsequent purge of the eastern Satraps was based on the argument that they had illegally used imperial funds to their own ends. The historical record and numismatic data point to a centralized authority over the Macedonian mints down to c. 317 BC, whereby Satraps were granted royal approval to mint coinage within very specific limits in the administration of their domains. This completely broke down with the death of Philip III Arrhidaios and the gradual process of increasing usurpation of royal authority by the successors.

access sufficient money to maintain the loyalty of his troops.⁵⁰ Only with the execution of Eumenes and Antigenes in early 316 BC, did the Susa treasury fall under Antigonos's control.⁵¹ The treasury held 15,000 talents of gold and silver that Antigonos transferred immediately to the fortress citadel and treasury of Kyinda in Kilikia, a facility that now fell under his direct control within his own satrapy.⁵² The solitary Group 4 issue from Aspeisas in the lead up to the surrender of the province of Susiana to Seleukos in 312/1 BC may represent all that could be sustained from the depleted treasury to fund a token resistance to the latter. Indeed, it is likely that Antigonos's decision to remove the entirety royal treasury at Susa to the fortress treasury at Kyinda contributed to the surrender of Susiana to Seleukos without a major struggle four years later. Without a substantial treasury at his disposal, the satrap Aspeisas would have been in no position to fund a meaningful resistance to Seleukos; a point highlighted by the solitary Group 4 issue from a single obverse die.

CONCLUSION

Weighing the numismatic evidence, together with the historical record, it is probable that Groups 1-3 date to the period c. 319/8-318/7 BC. This would account for the absence of the coinage from the Demanhur Hoard (318 BC), yet explain its appearance two years later in the Akçakale Hoard, for following the defeat of Eumenes the core of his army was redeployed by Antigonos, immediately dispersed into Asia Minor and beyond.⁵³ Group 4 definitely falls within the period 317/6-312/1 BC, most probably in the last year of this date range, prompted by Aspeisas's consideration of a token resistance to Seleukos I's expansion from Babylonia into Susiana.

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⁵⁰ Billows (1990): 91-93 and Waterfield (2011): 97.

⁵¹ Grainger: 48 '... Antigonos occupied the citadel from which Xenophilos had defied him the year before, and happily counted the money he thereby acquired. It came to 15,000 talents worth of art objects, 5,000 talents of coin and crowns to add to the 5,000 talents of silver he had collected from Ekbatana.'

⁵² Grainger (1990): 48, plus Billows (1997):106 & 256 citing *Diodoros* 19.48, 5-8 and 19.55, 1.

⁵³ Bosworth (2002): 159-160 and Bosworth (2002): 235. The latter makes the case that a component of *Argyraspides* were garrisoned by Antigonos at Carrhae, in northern Mesopotamia, in the aftermath of the Battle of Gabiene. Carrhae is located a short distance to the south of *Akçakale*.

This study had its genesis in the company of Eike Taylor. It is to his memory that I dedicate this work.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bellinger, A. R. 1951. An Alexander Hoard from Byblos. *Berytus* X: 37-49.
- Bellinger, A. R. 1963. *Essays on the Coinage of Alexander the Great*. Numismatic Studies No. II. New York: The American Numismatic Society.
- Billows, R. A. 1997. *Antigonos the One-Eyed and the Creation of the Hellenistic State*. Berkley: University of California Press.
- Bosworth, A. B. 2002. *The Legacy of Alexander. Politics, Warfare and Propaganda under the Successors*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Callataÿ, F. de. 2011. Quantifying Monetary Production in Greco-Roman Times: A General Frame, in F. de Callataÿ (ed.) *Quantifying Monetary Supplies in Greco-Roman Times: 7-29*. Pragmateiai 19. Bari: Edipuglia.
- Esty, W. W. 2006. How to Estimate the Original Number of Dies and the Coverage of a Sample. *Numismatic Chronicle* 166: 359-364.
- Esty, W. W. 2011. The Geometric Model for Estimating the Number of Dies, in F. de Callataÿ (ed.) *Quantifying Monetary Supplies in Greco-Roman Times: 43-58*. Pragmateiai 19. Bari: Edipuglia.
- Grainger, J. D. 1990. *Seleukos Nikator Constructing a Hellenistic Kingdom*. London and New York: Routledge, 2014 reprint of the original 1990 edition.
- Grainger, J. D. 2014. *The Rise of the Seleukid Empire 323-223 BC*. Barnsley, UK: Pen & Sword History.
- Houghton, A. and C. Lorber. 2002. *Seleucid Coins A Comprehensive Catalogue Part I Seleucus I through Antiochus III* Volumes I and II. New York and Lancaster, Pennsylvania: The American Numismatic Society and Classical Numismatic Group, Inc.
- Le Rider, G. 2007. *Alexander the Great: Coinage, Finances and Policy*. Translated by W. E. Higgins. Philadelphia: American Philosophical Society.
- Le Rider, G. and N. Olçay, 1988. Un trésor de tétradrachmes d'Alexandre trouvé à Akçakale en 1958. *Revue Numismatique* 30: 42-54.
- Miller, R. P. 2010. East Arachosia (Quetta) Hoard, 2002 (CH 10.275), in O. Hoover, A. Meadows and U. Wartenberg (eds.) *Coin Hoards Volume X Greek Hoards: 105-114*. New York: The American Numismatic Society.
- Nelson, B. R. 2010. Commerce ('Seleucus I') Hoard (CH 10.265), in O. Hoover, A. Meadows and U. Wartenberg (eds.) *Coin Hoards Volume X Greek Hoards: 731-104*. New York: The American Numismatic Society.
- Newell, E. T. 1923. *Alexander Hoards II Demanhur, 1905*. American Numismatic Society Numismatic Notes and Monographs No. 19. New York: American Numismatic Society.
- Newell, E. T. 1938. *The Coinage of the Eastern Seleucid Mints from Seleucus I to Antiochus III*. Numismatic Studies No. 1. New York: American Numismatic Society, 1978 reprint of the 1938 original.
- Price, M. J. 1991. *The Coinage in the Name of Alexander the Great and Philip Arrhidæus*. London: British Museum/Swiss Numismatic Society.
- Robinson, E. S. G. 1921. Aspeisas, Satrap of Susiana. *Numismatic Chronicle and Journal of the Royal Numismatic Society* 1 (1/2): 37-38.
- Romm, J. 2011. *Ghost on the Throne, The Death of Alexander the Great and the War for Crown and Empire*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
- Taylor, L. W. H. 2015. From Triparadeisos to Ipsos: Seleukos I Nikator's Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia. *American Journal of Numismatics* Second Series 27: 41-97.
- Taylor, L. W. H. 2018. A Philip III Tetradrachm Die Pair Recycled by Seleukos I. *Koinon* 1: 39-46.

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- Taylor, L. W. H. 2019. The Susa Wreath Group Alexanders: The First Step in the Transformation of an Anchor Seal into a Dynastic Emblem. *Koinon* 2: 63-82.
- Taylor, L. W. H. in prep. On the Reattribution of the Berytos Alexanders to Byblos.
- Waterfield, R. 2011. *Dividing the Spoils. The War for Alexander the Great's Empire*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.